

was conducted at the ordinary temperature without any halogen carrier, the yield was 4.3 g.

4-Chloro-6-bromo-m-xylene.—To 4-chloro-*m*-xylene (2 c. c.) and bromine (1 c.c.) in a flask and heated on a water bath, nitro-sulphonic acid mixture (1 c.c.) was added drop by drop and the heating continued for half an hour more. The product was worked up as described above. The crystals from ether melted at 68° and were identified to be 4-chloro-6-bromo-*m*-xylene, yield 3 g. In presence of sodium nitrite and fuming sulphuric acid the yield was 2.8 g. and in presence of iodine as carrier 2.6 g.

2-Chloro-5-bromo-p-xylene.—To 2-chloro-*p*-xylene (3 c.c.) and bromine (1 c. c.) in a flask, nitro-sulphonic acid mixture (1 c.c.) was added drop by drop and heated on a water bath for about 45 minutes. The chloro-bromo compound was obtained as described above and the crystals separated by cooling in a freezing mixture, m. p. 66°, yield 3.1 g. With strong nitric acid the yield was 2.8 g.

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Parachor and Chemical Constitution. Part II. The Structure of the Triphenylmethane Dyes.

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The constitution of the triphenylmethane dyes has been the subject of much controversy, the problem being not yet settled. The mother substances of the group, triphenylmethane and triphenyl carbinol are colourless. The *leuco*-bases as well as the dye-bases (when freshly prepared) are also colourless, while the salts are intensely coloured substances. It thus appears that there must be some fundamental difference in structure between the colourless and the coloured compounds. The colourless compounds are represented by benzenoid configuration while various formulæ have been proposed

from time to time by different investigators for the coloured salts of which the following are the most important :

.Rosaniline hydrochloride.

(Fischer, *Ber.*, 1878, 11, 1079; 1879, 12, 2351) $P_{\text{calc}} = 724.0$

(Nietzki, "Organische Farbstoffe," 1888.) $P_{\text{calc}} = 741.1$.

(Rosentishi, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1880, 33, 342, 426). $P_{\text{calc}} = 717.9$

The present work was undertaken with a view to find out which of the above formulæ agrees with the parachor contribution of the various triphenylmethane derivatives. The mother substance triphenyl carbinol, and the hydrochlorides of *para*-rosaniline (triaminotriphenyl carbinol), rosaniline (triaminodiphenyltolyl carbinol), crystal violet (hexamethyl-triaminotriphenyl carbinol) and malachite green (tetramethyldiamino-triphenyl carbinol) have been studied. As the dye-bases cannot be kept colourless for a sufficiently long time in the air the coloured dye-bases of rosaniline and crystal violet, as well as the *leuco*-base of malachite green, have also been investigated.

The surface tension was determined by the method of maximum bubble pressure as in the previous works. As the compounds decompose on fusion, it is not possible to determine their parachor in the fused state. The density and surface tension were determined in solution (Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 671) and the parachor calculated from the results obtained, P_x , was found to vary, except in a few cases, with x , the required parachor being obtained from the curve drawn by plotting P_x against x and finding the point of intersection with the ($x=0$) axis as in the previous work on carbohydrates (Ray, *ibid.*, 1934, 11, 843). It will be found that with crystal violet colour-base and malachite green hydrochloride in pyridine, the value of P_x gradually increases with the increase of x , instead of decreasing. The required parachor can not be obtained in these cases from the curves as the point of intersection with the ($x=1$) axis can not be found, the points being too far from the ($x=1$) axis and too near the ($x=0$) axis, the solutions being extremely dilute.

It will be evident from the results given below that the parachor contributions of the coloured salts of the triphenylmethane agree with the quinonoid formula of Neitzki. Thus it appears that in solution these coloured salts possess the quinonoid configuration.

It is of much interest to note that the parachor values also suggest the quinonoid structure for the coloured dye-bases. In this connection it is to be noted that Georgievics (*Monatsh.*, 1896, 17, 4) in the case of magenta, and Homolka in the case of 'New Fuchsin' discovered a second rosaniline base which is coloured. The existence of this second rosaniline base was shown by Hantzsch and Ostwald (*Ber.*, 1900, 33, 278) by electrical conductivity experiments.

Little work appears to have been done on the phenomenon of the change of colour of the dry carbinol-bases in presence of air. It was found that air is necessary for this colour change, as they can be kept colourless for a sufficiently long time in a vacuum desiccator. It was also found that this change is extremely rapid in the case of the carbinol base of crystal violet, while with the rosaniline base it is somewhat sluggish.

The author is of opinion that this change of colour is due to the migration of the OH group from the methane-carbon atom to a nitrogen atom of the amino group with the necessary transformation into the quinonoid configuration. It is difficult to explain the mechanism of this change; probably carbonic acid is instrumental in bringing about this transformation in the following way:

the carbonate being momentarily formed and then decomposed. This view is supported by the fact that colour appears rapidly when carbon dioxide is passed into the colourless solution while with oxygen the appearance of colour was not noted for a sufficiently long time. Moreover, the observations made by Georgievics (*loc. cit.*) that the solutions of coloured bases and the corresponding solution of the hydrochloride possess identical dyeing properties appear to suggest that the two have the same configuration. The structure suggested for the coloured bases by Georgievics (*loc. cit.*) is not in accordance with the results obtained by Weil (*Ber.*, 1896, 29, 1541) and by the present author.

It will be seen that in the malachite green series, the variation of P_x is somewhat large. This is due probably to the presence of traces of impurities in these compounds as it is extremely difficult to purify them.

In the following tables x denotes the molar fraction of the solute, M_m , the mean molecular weight of the solution, P_m , the mean parachor and P_x , the parachor of the solute. The mean temperature of observation is about 28°. The results within parentheses are obtained from the curves given below.

TABLE I.

Triphenyl carbinol in pyridine.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	$P_{\text{calc.}}$
0.0	0.9787	36.30	79.00	199.2	...	
0.006251	0.9754	36.36	80.11	201.7	607.8	611.9
0.007723	0.9769	36.56	80.89	202.3	609.5	
0.008515	0.9777	36.55	80.59	202.5	610.6	
0.001182	0.9796	36.68	81.15	203.8	583.7	
0.01523	0.9814	36.77	81.76	205.1	584.3	

TABLE II.

Triphenyl carbinol in chloroform.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	$P_{calc.}$
0.0	1.4640	25.97	119.87	184.1	...	
0.008151	1.4511	26.04	120.52	187.6	613.4	611.9
0.009795	1.4506	26.21	120.75	188.3	612.7	
0.01191	1.4502	26.34	121.09	189.2	612.8	
0.01530	1.4483	26.60	121.55	190.7	614.4	
0.02032	1.4398	26.57	122.18	192.7	611.0	

TABLE III.

Rosaniline hydrochloride in alcohol.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .
0.0	0.7893	22.03	46	126.4	...
0.001353	0.7912	22.21	46.39	127.3	739.2
0.001625	0.7917	22.25	46.42	127.4	737.7
0.002018	0.7922	22.30	46.56	127.7	743.3

mean 740.1

The calculated parachor for different formulæ has already been cited.

TABLE IV.

Rosaniline hydrochloride in alcohol.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .
0.0	0.7893	22.03	46	126.4	...
0.001803	0.7900	22.06	46.53	127.6	776.7
0.002307	0.7910	22.10	46.68	127.9	780.3
0.003479	0.7935	22.35	47.01	128.7	776.2
0.005533	0.7965	22.40	47.62	130.0	777.8

mean 777.6

The calculated parachor is as follows, parachor being shown in parenthesis: Quinonoid formula (780.1), Fischer's formula (763.0), Rosentiehl's formula (758.9).

TABLE V.

Rosaniline colour-base in pyridine.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .
0.0	0.9790	36.55	79	199.6	...
0.004279	0.9760	36.46	80.04	201.5	724.6
0.005034	0.9775	36.55	80.20	201.8	718.3
0.006036	0.9786	36.64	80.43	202.3	712.9
0.006823	0.9795	36.70	80.63	202.6	708.4
0.009170	0.9824	36.86	81.18	203.6	686.6
0.01397	0.9886	37.37	82.35	205.9	651.0
0.01416	0.9883	37.32	82.39	206.0	649.8
1.0	(758.0)

TABLE VI_a*Rosaniline colour-base in quinoline.*

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .
0.0	1.0941	44.67	180	307.2	...
0.005091	1.0943	44.80	180.85	309.5	766.1
0.006915	1.0942	44.96	181.11	310.3	762.4
0.007859	1.0944	44.90	181.80	310.7	763.5
0.009206	1.0952	45.16	181.51	311.3	760.3
0.01015	1.0952	45.17	181.70	311.8	758.8
0.01296	1.0960	45.34	182.25	313.0	757.7

mean 761.5

The calculated parachor in parenthesis is as follows: Quinonoid formula (762.9), Fischer's formula (745.8), Rosentiehl's formula (789.7).

TABLE VII.

Crystal violet hydrochloride in pyridine.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .
0·0	0·9737	36·30	79	199·2	...
0·003000	0·9760	36·48	79·98	201·4	933·3
0·003460	0·9765	36·51	80·15	201·8	924·7
0·005940	0·9785	36·50	80·93	203·8	892·3
0·007112	0·9805	36·56	81·35	204·0	871·8
0·008147	0·9816	36·63	81·59	204·5	859·2
1·0	(976·0)

TABLE VIII.

Crystal violet hydrochloride in chloroform.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .
0·0	1·4640	25·97	119·37	184·1	...
0·002880	1·4609	26·17	120·27	186·2	935·4
0·004535	1·4592	26·24	120·75	187·4	926·0
0·005943	1·4563	26·31	121·12	188·3	891·9
0·007191	1·4557	26·38	121·43	189·0	876·0
0·01087	1·4549	26·52	122·53	191·0	818·5
1·0	(975·0)

The calculated parachor in parentheses is as follows:—Quinonoid formula (975·1), Fischer's formula (958·0), Rosentiehl's formula (951·9).

TABLE IX.

Crystal violet colour-base in pyridine.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .
0·0	0·9737	36·30	79	199·2	...
0·003546	0·9790	36·80	80·10	201·5	817·2
0·005720	0·9810	36·83	80·77	202·8	823·7
0·006723	0·9817	36·80	81·07	203·4	838·0
0·009122	0·9832	37·18	81·64	205·0	844·1

TABLE X.

Crystal violet colour-base in chloroform.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .
0.0	1.4703	26.98	119.37	184.1	...
0.004488	1.4662	26.85	120.65	187.4	935.6
0.005610	1.4637	26.98	120.98	188.3	926.8
0.006725	1.4620	26.98	121.22	189.0	921.9
0.008110	1.4604	27.10	121.55	190.0	912.0
0.009387	1.4573	27.14	121.85	190.9	905.5
1.0	(957.1)

The calculated parachor in parenthesis is as follows:—Quinonoid formula (957.9), Fischer's formula (940.8), Rosenthiel's formula (934.7).

TABLE XI.

Malachite green leuco-base in pyridine.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	P_{calc} .
0.0	0.9737	36.30	79	199.2	...	
0.603203	0.9799	36.77	79.75	201.3	841.6	637.1
0.005298	0.9809	37.53	80.09	202.6	830.7	
0.005613	0.9810	37.43	80.41	202.6	837.5	
0.005758	0.9812	37.46	80.44	202.9	833.4	
0.01248	0.9843	38.25	82.11	207.3	842.6	
				mean	837.2	

TABLE XII.

Malachite green hydrochloride in pyridine.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .
0.0	0.9737	36.30	79	199.2	...
0.004112	0.9770	36.34	80.16	201.4	729.7
0.005226	0.9783	36.36	80.47	202.1	746.3
0.005443	0.9806	36.81	80.56	202.3	752.6
0.006615	0.9816	36.81	80.88	202.9	756.0
0.007608	0.9820	36.67	81.16	203.5	762.3

TABLE XIII.

Malachite green hydrochloride in nitrobenzene.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	$Mm.$	$P_m.$	$P_x.$
0.0	1.1997	42.36	123	261.4	...
0.003858	1.2010	43.06	124.01	263.8	907.8
0.004416	1.1996	42.66	124.11	264.2	905.9
0.006258	1.2020	43.01	124.48	265.3	894.8
0.006628	1.2022	43.09	124.62	265.5	890.2
0.007008	1.2034	43.20	124.6	265.8	899.1
					mean 899.6

The calculated parachor in parenthesis is as follows:—Quinonoid formula (897.5), Fischer's formula, (880.4), Rosentiehl's formula, (874.3).

1. Rosaniline colour-base in pyridine
2. Crystal violet hydrochloride "
3. Do Do in $CHCl_3$
4. Do colour-base "
5. Do Do in pyridine
6. Malachite green hydrochloride .. "

SUMMARY.

1. The surface tension and density of the hydrochlorides and coloured carbinol-bases of rosaniline, crystal violet and malachite green have been determined in solution and the parachor calculated.

2. The parachor values were found to agree with the quinonoid structure suggested by Nietzki.

My grateful thanks are due to Prof. P. R. Ray of the University College of Science and to Prof. A. Maitra of the Presidency College for the kind interest they took in the work.

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A Yellow Colouring Matter from the Wood of *Adina Cordifolia*, Hook.

BY JAGARAJ BEHARI LAL AND SIKHIBHUSEAN DUTT.

Adina cordifolia (Hook) which is known as "Keli-Kadam" in Bengal and "Naldu" in Hindusthani, is a large deciduous tree which is found to be fairly well distributed throughout the whole of northern India as well as Bengal, Assam and Burma. In most of the forests it grows profusely and very often it is planted as a road-side or avenue tree. The wood is very even-grained, moderately hard, lemon-yellow in colour when freshly cut but turning yellowish grey on exposure and weighs 45 pounds per cubic foot. It is suitable for furniture making and in northern India combs are made out of this wood as well as toys and drums. The colouring matter of this wood is very easily removed by extraction with boiling water or organic solvents and as no work seems to have been done before on this subject, the present investigation was undertaken with a view to the isolation of the colouring matter in a pure state and elucidation of its constitution.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A big log of the authentic specimen of the wood was procured from Messrs. Bhupat Lal & Sons, Wood Merchants, Allahabad, and was converted into shavings. For exhaustive extraction with